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3 RESCALE Info Days and Stakeholder Engagement

3 In 2026, RESCALE strengthened its engagement with the European cybersecurity and computing-systems community through two major stakeholder events.

3 At **HiPEAC 2026 in Kraków**, RESCALE organised its **1st Info Day/workshop** dedicated to supply chain security, bringing together researchers, practitioners, and industry stakeholders to discuss evidence-based assurance, traceability, and “trust with proof”.
2 The project also presented on-site posters, sharing RESCALE’s vision, objectives, and progress with the wider HiPEAC community.

RESCALE also organised its **2nd Stakeholder Info Day in Helsinki** on 13 May 2026 as a hybrid event for industry, academia, public authorities, and cybersecurity experts. The event presented RESCALE results, demonstrated project tools, showcased pilots, and opened discussion on software and hardware supply chain security, including the implications of the EU Cyber Resilience Act for digital product assurance and compliance.

RESCALE Featured in HiPEACinfo #77

RESCALE was featured in HiPEACinfo #77 in the Innovation Europe section with the article “**Fortifying the foundation: RESCALE’s revolution in secure supply chains**”. The feature highlighted RESCALE’s secure-by-design approach, the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), and the project’s contribution to scalable, evidence-based, and auditable supply chain security across hardware and software ecosystems, helping communicate RESCALE’s objectives and results to a wider European research and industry audience.

RESCALE Standardisation White Paper Released

Another important achievement was the release of the [RESCALE Standardisation White Paper](#). The white paper presents RESCALE’s holistic cybersecurity framework, the TBOM concept, blockchain-based trust mechanisms, and the project’s alignment with key regulatory and standardisation developments, including the Cyber Resilience Act, NIS2, ETSI, IETF SCITT, and CEN-CENELEC.

This publication provides a strong basis for dialogue with the standardisation community and demonstrates how RESCALE’s results can contribute to improved practices in supply chain security, certification, trust management, and secure-by-design digital products.

Since the beginning of 2026 , RESCALE has organised the following project meetings:

- 5th Plenary Meeting, Kraków, hosted by SPHYNX
- 6th Plenary Meeting, Helsinki, hosted by Binare
- S&T meetings, hosted by AEGIS
- Consortium meetings

Horizon Booster Services Successfully Completed

A total of **3** Horizon Booster Services were successfully completed:

- **Service 3.5 – Audio-Visual Support:** RESCALE successfully completed this service with the production of [the project’s official promotional video](#), presenting its objectives and ambition to strengthen cyber resilience through innovative research.
- **Service 3.1 – NET Support Service: Networking & Ecosystem Building:** RESCALE completed this service to strengthen connections with key stakeholders, innovation ecosystems, and relevant communities, supporting greater visibility, collaboration opportunities, and long-term impact.
- **Go2Market Programme – Module D: Business Plan:** RESCALE successfully completed this module, refining its business strategy, exploitation potential, and future approach to industry engagement and real-world uptake.

Publications

33 total publications have been submitted by RESCALE partners in the 1st/2nd/3rd year. An indicative list follows:

- Trust Score Prediction for IoT Device Onboarding Using Transfer and Few-Shot Learning in Consumer Electronics. <https://zenodo.org/records/17520726>
- From vulnerability to resilience: Adversarial training and real-time detection for AI security. <https://zenodo.org/records/17521005>
- PINSA: Privacy-preserving cyber insurance framework. <https://zenodo.org/records/19331441>
- Dynamic Detection of Vulnerable DMA Race Conditions. <https://zenodo.org/records/17855037>
- Suspicious Minds: Psychological Techniques Correlated with Online Phishing Attacks. <https://zenodo.org/records/17120650>
- CRASHED: Cyber risk assessment for smart home electronic devices. <https://zenodo.org/records/17120337>
- Phantom Trails: Practical Pre-Silicon Discovery of Transient Data Leaks. <https://zenodo.org/records/17009888>
- hwdbg: Debugging Hardware Like Software. <https://zenodo.org/records/17009872>

For more information about the project deliverables and publications, visit RESCALE's Zenodo community: [RESCALE Project](#)

Collaboration

The collaboration between RESCALE and the Horizon Europe project CyberSecDome has further progressed through active participation in joint dissemination and clustering activities. **RESCALE participated in the 2nd edition of CyberSecDome's Cluster Synergies Webinar**, held online on 22 April 2026, contributing to knowledge exchange with other EU-funded cybersecurity projects and strengthening links within the European cybersecurity research and innovation ecosystem.

In addition, **CyberSecDome presented its work during RESCALE's first Info Day**, organised as part of the RESCALE HIPEAC 2026 workshop in Kraków. This mutual participation reflects the growing cooperation between the two projects and supports the identification of synergies, increased visibility, and future opportunities for joint communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities.

Events

RESCALE has participated in the following events during 2026 so far:

- Plenary meeting of CEN-CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain
- HIPEAC 2026
- "AI Enables Cybersecurity" Meetup
- Joint meeting of ETSI CYBER-EUSR and CEN-CENELEC
- SecOPERA plenary
- Meetings with national Standardisation Bodies

Contact Project Coordinator: Dr. Apostolos Fournaris, Industrial Systems Institute (ISI), fournaris@isi.gr
General Inquiries: [Website Contact Form](#)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No **101120962**.

